

Workify: Remote Work Tracker

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Abstract:- Standups are an integral part of every developer working in a startup company. Standups are a type of developer's meeting where they share their progress on what they were working on yesterday, what they will be working on today, and so on. Standups used to be in the physical form, but after lockdown, they changed to online mode. As most of the startup snow have gone W.F.H, they still follow online standups and the main problem with this is that it takes a lot of time to complete, and sometimes it's become boring for others to listen to it. So to overcome this, we are developing a Remote first work tracker to help developers to add their daily tasks on this application where they can drag and drop their work between days as this application follows a calendar format. With this, the application also supports the agile project model, where the developer can lineup the tasks to complete the project and track them.

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication is of utmost importance in any team. When it comes to tech teams managing your work as well as having an idea of the tasks you have assigned is crucial. Dev Ops is the combination of cultural philosophies, practices, and tools that increases an organization's ability to deliver applications and services at high velocity: evolving and improving products at a faster pace than organizations using traditional software development and infrastructure management processes. SCRUM is the most widely used software development method o logy in organizations. Scrum is a framework for project management that emphasizes teamwork, accountability and iterative progress toward a well-defined goal. Our system helps solve this problem for both the developer as well as the manager. A developer needs to keep track of all the assignments he hasbeen assigned as well as how much work he/she has already completed. The framework begins with a simple premise: Start with what can be seen or known. After that, track the progress and tweak, as necessary. A Kanban board is an essential tool for tracking development progress. A Kanban board is an agile project management tool designed to help visualize work in progress, and maximize efficiency (or flow). It can help both agile and Dev Ops teams establish order in their daily work.

II. LITERATURESURVEY

Existing Systems: The features in this system are already implemented in some other softwares such as Google calendar which has a calendar, Trello application which powers the Kanban system and the Jira software which has scrum andbugs system to integrate in it. User need to use this separate applications in order to use the features of our application. Even though all the features are

implemented before hand they are present on different platforms and if user wants to use all the features at once then the user has to use this all platform at once which will be very hectic to use and also very challenging. Also, the Jira software allows users to either uses crumorbug for a single workflow, if user want to use this both then they have to make 2 new projects. None of the systems have support for the GitHub.

III. BACKGROUND

With the help of our software, IT firms and Startups can maintain and track their project progress. It helps IT teams to plan, assign, track, report and manage work. Our software also helps individuals/teams to organize events as planning, assigning and tracking work becomes easy and efficient. Open-source contributions trends among new developers are increasing day by day and with this increase in open source, managing becomes a challenge, and with Workify, this challenge becomes easy as GitHub issues can be raised and solved from this same software with project management. A Dev Ops application helps Managers assign tasks to developers as well as help developers keep track of assigned tasks. Scrumis one of the agile methodologies designed to guide teams in the iterative and incremental delivery of a product. Often referred to as "anagile project management framework,"

Its focus is on the use of an empirical process that allows teams to respond rapidly, efficiently and effectively to change. Facilitated key features like SCRUM to maintain the agile process of development. Kanban is a popular Lean work flow management method for defining, managing and improving services that deliver knowledge work. It helps you visualize work, maximize efficiency, and improve continuously. Work is represented on Kanban boards, allowing you to optimize work delivery across multiple teams and handle even the most complex projects in a single environment. Utilized the KANBAN board showing work items at anytime.

IV. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

This proposed system is going to developed completely based on Type script. For the frontend and server we are using Next. js, styling-Tail windcss, api-GraphQL, database-Supabase. Complete solution is created using Type script, Thus, there are a bunch of typescript based libraries used in the solution as well. Passport-google-oauth2: This library is used for google authentication of the user, using Google as the gateway. Bcrypt: This library is used to bcrypt and dcrypt the password of the users to red in the database. Nookies: This library is used to store the cookie in the web cookies, based on this cookie is user is given access to the routes. Json web token: This library is used to create 32 bit code which is used to create a token

with has a link to the id of the user for authentication. Yup: This library is used for validating the use input for the front end as well as the backend. We will start with a landing page describing the application followed by the login or registration page as per the user selection. After the user is logged in successfully, the user will be directed to the dashboard page where the user can create a project or search project. The user can create a project and keep it private or public based on which it will be accessible to other users. The project page will be having all the main functionality of our project. Here the user can update the work the user is currently working on with the help of a calendar view, or the user can track the task using the Kanban board or can create as crums print to complete the task in a given time, or can track the bugs found. In Kanban the user can create task,

update task, assign the task to other user to complete the task, share the task and can delete the task. The user who have created the project will have the authority to add other users to the group. In scrum the user can create task, update task, assign the task to other user to complete the task, share the task and can delete the task. The bug feature will the option to integrate Git Hub to it so that all the issues can be raised directly from this single application. In the project settings the user can select with feature to user and can change the the me and status of project from public to private and vicea versa. Modules: 1.Login Module 2.Registration Module 3.User Dashboard Module 4. Project Module 5. Calendar Module 6. Kanban Module 7. Scrum Module 8. Bug Module.

Fig. 1: Dashboard

Fig. 2: Kanban

Fig. 3: Backlog Scrum

Fig. 4: Scrum Board

Fig. 5: Calendar

V. FUTURE SCOPE

GitHub is a code hosting platform for version control and collaboration. It lets you and others work together on projects from anywhere. This tutorial teaches you Git Hub essentials like repositories, branches, commits and pull requests. Git Hub is a web-based service for version control using Git. Basically, it is a social networking site for developers. You can look at other people's code, identify issues with their code and even propose changes. Git Hub is used by developers and companies to build, ship, and maintain software. It makes it possible to collaborate and share code and keep tabs of what's changed along the way. This process can make it easy to track down, say, when or how a bug was introduced. Creating harmony in the work flow and increasing efficiency of teams is the goal of our system.

VI. CONCLUSION

Making a Dev Ops web app using multiple web development technologies to help both managers and developers. Facilitating most of the major features required by development teams such as Scrum, Kanban, Calendar. Created a strong base for further addition of essential features like Git Hub collaboration. Our further future scope is Slack App integration which is a widely used in IT firms, where the user can send the updated of the task directly to the slack thread from the application and Notion Integration which is used by project management with the notion the user can create tasks on the notion and directly import the task in this application.

REFERENCES

- [1.] "What Makes Agile Software Development Agile?", IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering (Volume:48, Issue:9, 01 September 2022).
- [2.] "Scrum model for agile methodology", 2017 International Conference on Computing, Communication and Automation (ICCCA).
- [3.] [3]"Dev Ops", May-June 2016, pp. 94-100, vol.33.
- [4.] [4]"Boris Cherny on Type Script", IEEE Software (Volume:37, Issue:2, March-April 2020)